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AGRICULTURAL STATISTICAL REPORT ON CROP CULTIVATION FOR SEASON A 2025 IN FY 2025/2026.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Department of Production routinely monitors agricultural production and productivity by collecting data on seasonal production and productivity indicators, as outlined in the Agricultural Extension Grant guidelines.

To improve efficiency and accuracy, a digital data collection tool was developed to facilitate the seasonal collection, management, and analysis of agricultural data.

This report presents the findings for Season A 2025, highlighting key performance indicators related to crop production, pest and disease incidence, Agricultural extension services, agricultural technology uptake, access to communication assets and food security analysis. The information is intended to inform planning, decision-making, and targeted interventions aimed at enhancing agricultural productivity and farmer livelihoods in the district.

2.0. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Study Area and Data Collection

The surveillance was conducted among farming households across the lower local governments of Kayunga District. Data was collected from August to December 2025 for Season A. (January–July 2025) of FY 2025/2026. Information gathered included socio-economic characteristics, major pest and disease incidences, and the control measures adopted by farmers.

2.2. Survey Methodology

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed with Kobo Toolbox, a web-based platform that supports both online and offline data collection.

The questionnaire was distributed via a web link shared through the Kayunga District Production Department WhatsApp group, the Kayunga District Crop WhatsApp group, the Kayunga District PDM WhatsApp group, and individual WhatsApp contacts of Agricultural Extension Officers in the Kayunga District Local Government.

2.3. Sample Size and Selection of respondents for the survey

A stratified sampling approach was employed, with households grouped by lower local government units to ensure adequate representation across the study area. Household population data from the 2014 Population and Housing Census were used to determine the proportion of households in each stratum. Sample sizes were then allocated proportionally to each stratum based on the total number of households. Within each

stratum, households were selected using simple random sampling. The household served as the unit of observation and data collection.

Sub-County/Town Council	Total household(N)	Sample households(n)	No. parishes	HH/Parish	No. of Villages	HH per Village
Bbaale	3805	362	6	60	27	13
Galiraya	5068	371	6	62	38	10
Kayonza	11739	387	9	43	73	5
Kitimbwa SC & TC	8975	383	7	55	48	8
Busaana SC& TC	10612	385	8	48	48	8
Kangulumira SC &TC	11354	386	6	64	37	10
Kayunga S/C	8799	383	8	48	48	8
Kayunga S/C	6852	378	4	94	18	21
Nazigo SC&TC	8964	383	7	55	48	8
Total	76168	3418	61	529	385	92

N=No. of Households, n = Sample households

Table 1. Distribution of sample households for the different lower local governments

2.4. Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel 2019. Results were summarized using counts and percentages and presented in tables and charts. A total of 399 valid submissions were used for the analysis.

3.0. RESULTS

3.1. Number and Percentage of Respondents, by Sex of Household Head.

Out of the 399 respondents interviewed, 217 (54.39%) were male household heads, while 182 (45.61%) were female. The majority of respondents, 204 (51.13%), were drawn from Kayunga Sub-county. In contrast, Busaana Town Council recorded the lowest representation, with only one respondent (0%). No responses were recorded from Kitimbwa Town Council, Kitimbwa Sub-county, or Nazigo Sub-county (Table 2).

3.2. Average Household Size and Access to Telephones

The average household size among the surveyed respondents was 5.18 persons. With regard to communication assets, 318 respondents (95%) reported owning a mobile telephone. The remaining 18 respondents (5%) did not own a mobile phone but indicated that they had access to one through another household member or external sources.

Lower Local Government name	Female	Male	Grand Total
Bbaale SC	1	2	3
Busaana SC	7	10	17
Busaana TC	0	1	1
Galiraya SC	12	14	26
Kangulumira SC	3	4	7
Kangulumira TC	1	5	6
Kayonza SC	43	67	110
Kayunga SC	99	105	204
Kayunga TC	4	2	6
Nazigo TC	12	7	19
Grand Total	182	217	399

Table 2. Distribution of respondents by sex and location (n=399).

3.3. The Main Purpose of Crop Production

Crop production remains a major component of household livelihoods, serving both subsistence needs and income generation for a large proportion of the population. Results show that nearly 80% of all households engage in crop production primarily for a dual purpose of own consumption and sale to the market, which demonstrates the mixed subsistence–commercial nature of agricultural systems in Kayunga. This production strategy enables households to meet food requirements while also generating income to support other livelihood needs.

In contrast, approximately 10% of households reported producing crops exclusively for market-oriented purposes, reflecting a smaller but notable segment of more commercially focused farmers. Overall, the distribution of production purposes highlights the predominance of semi-subsistence farming, with limited full commercialisation among the surveyed households.

Figure 1. Percentage distribution of households according to their main purpose of production (n = 399)

3.4. Crops Cultivated by Households

A mixture of staple food and cash crops characterized household crop production during Season A of 2025. The majority of surveyed households reported cultivating maize, coffee, beans, bananas, and cassava, reflecting both subsistence and income-oriented farming systems in Kayunga District. In addition to these major crops, a limited number of households produced horticultural crops, including mangoes, oranges, and watermelons.

Maize, identified as a priority crop in Kayunga District, was the most widely cultivated crop during Season A of 2025, with more than half of the respondents reporting its production (Figure 2). Its widespread cultivation indicates its dual role as a staple food and a source of household income. Coffee, the principal cash crop in the district, was cultivated by nearly half of all the surveyed households, highlighting its continued importance in household livelihoods.

Beans, a critical food security crop due to their nutritional value and role in household diets, were grown by approximately 40% of all the respondents during Season A of 2025.

The cultivation of bananas and cassava by a substantial proportion of households highlights the importance of resilient, perennial, and drought-tolerant crops in ensuring food availability. Overall, the crop production patterns observed during the season show a diversified farming system that supports both household food security and income generation.

Figure 2: Number of Households that cultivated the different crops for Season A 2025 FY25/26, (n=399).

3.5. Total Land Size Cultivated by Crop Enterprise

Out of the total 1,170.3 acres of agricultural land available, 1,080.32 acres (92.31%) were cultivated under various crop enterprises during Season A 2025. The distribution of cultivated land varied considerably among the different crops (Figure 3).

Maize accounted for the largest share of cultivated land at 31%, followed by beans (23%) and coffee (21%). Together, these three crops occupied approximately 75% of the total cultivated area, indicating a strong emphasis on food and cash crop production.

The remaining cultivated land was allocated to a range of other crops, including banana, cassava, pineapple, rice, groundnuts, sugarcane, vegetables, and fruits. However, individual crops such as cabbage, watermelon, mangoes, green pepper, oranges, and papaya each occupied less than 1% of the total cultivated area.

Overall, the land allocation pattern shows a production system dominated by a few major crops, with limited land devoted to high-value horticultural enterprises.

Figure 3: Percentage share of total cultivated land allocated to each crop enterprise during Season A 2025, FY 2025/26 (n = 1,080.32).

3.6. Land Productivity for Season A 2025

Land productivity during Season A 2025 was generally low across most crop enterprises, as presented in Table 3. Almost all the enterprises performed extremely below the expected yield per acre. Considerable variation in production per acre was observed among the different crops cultivated during the season (Figure 4).

Industrial sugarcane registered the highest productivity at 7.14 tons per acre. This was followed by watermelon, which attained a productivity of 3.20 tons per acre. Vegetable crops, particularly green pepper (2.27 tons per acre) and cabbage (2.19 tons per acre), recorded relatively fair productivity compared to other enterprises.

Moderate productivity levels were observed in sweet potatoes (2.10 tons per acre) and oranges (1.90 tons per acre). Fruit crops such as banana (1.48 tons per acre), pineapple (1.24 tons per acre), and papaya (0.55 tons per acre) performed below expected yield potential. Staple food crops, including maize (0.64 tons per acre), beans (0.20 tons per acre), rice (0.42 tons per acre), and soybeans (0.23 tons per acre) recorded low productivity levels.

The lowest productivity was reported in non-industrial sugarcane (0.08 tons per acre) and vanilla (0.05 tons per acre), suggesting significant agronomic, climatic, or management constraints during the season.

Overall, the results indicate that while a few crops achieved relatively good yields, the majority of crop enterprises performed below optimal productivity levels, highlighting the need for improved agronomic practices.

S/N	Crop	Total Area/Acreage	Total Production (kilogram)	Production per Acre (tonnes)
1	Sugarcane Industrial	14	100000	7.14
2	Watermelon	0.5	1600	3.20
3	Green Paper	3.75	8500	2.27
4	Cabbage	5	10944	2.19
5	Sweetpotatoe	8.84	18560	2.10
6	Oranges	0.25	475	1.90
7	Tomatoes	18.22	30315	1.66
8	Banana	57.38	84700	1.48
9	Pineapple	53.35	66220	1.24
10	Cassava	78.05	87086.2	1.12
11	Maize	329.9	211141	0.64
12	Coffee	226.4	137729	0.61
13	Jackfruit	1	583	0.58
14	Papaya	3.25	1800	0.55
15	Ground nuts	18.5	7845	0.42
16	Rice	6.5	2736.2	0.42
17	Mangoes	0.5	190	0.38
18	Soy bean	2	450	0.23
19	Beans	250.93	49898	0.20
20	Sugarcane non-industrial	1	80	0.08
21	Vanilla	1	50	0.05

Table 3: Shows the productivity of the different crop enterprises during Season A 2025

Figure 4. Production per acre in tons of the different crop enterprises in season A 2025.

3.7. Agricultural Technology Uptake.

The majority of respondents reported adopting at least one form of improved agricultural technology. Specifically, 87% of all the respondents indicated that they used improved seeds or planting materials, while 85% reported using pesticides or herbicides. Fertilizer application was reported by 89% of all the respondents, indicating a high level of uptake of soil fertility management practices. In contrast, the use of irrigation technologies remained very low, with only 2% of respondents reporting use of irrigation during the season A 2025. (Figure 5).

Figure 5: Responses on the use of the different agricultural technologies among households (n = 399).

3.8. Land Under Irrigation.

Out of the total cultivated land area of 1,080.32 acres, only 81.9 acres (7.58%) were under irrigation. Among the nine respondents who practiced irrigation, the majority reported using watering cans and sprinkler irrigation systems, accounting for nearly 40% of all the responses. No respondents reported using flood irrigation methods (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Types of irrigation used by farmers (n=16)

3.9. Access to Agricultural Production Services in Season A 2025.

Household manual labour is the main source of farm labour, accounting for 20% of all responses (Figure. 7). This labour is mostly unpaid and provided by family members, showing a continued reliance on household labour for agricultural production.

Hired manual labour accounted for nearly 12% of all the responses, indicating that agriculture not only provides food and cash crops but also paid employment opportunities within the community.

Nearly 20% of all the responses reported ownership of tarpaulins, reflecting improved post-harvest handling practices. Tarpaulins are especially important for drying crops such as maize and beans.

Agricultural mechanization remains limited. Tractor hire accounted for 17% of all the responses, while the use of ox-ploughs accounted for 13%. This shows restricted access to mechanized and animal-drawn power, which may limit timely land preparation hence overall productivity.

Figure 7. Ownership and accessibility of the different agricultural production services. (Owned n=345, Hired n=447).

3.10. Access to Agricultural Extension Services

Of the 399 respondents surveyed, 345 (85.5%) reported having access to agricultural extension services, indicating a relatively high level of extension coverage within the study area (Figure 8).

However, 54 respondents (13.5%) reported not having access to any agricultural extension services, which may limit their exposure to improved technologies and to recommended good agricultural practices. It's important that such gaps are addressed to improve inclusivity and contribute to more uniform agricultural development across the study area.

Figure 8. Access to Agricultural extension services. (n=399)

3.11. Sources of Agricultural Extension Services

Among the 345 respondents who accessed agricultural extension services, nearly 50% received support from government extension workers, showing the dominant role of public extension in agricultural technology transfer and adoption. Less than 5% accessed services through non-governmental organizations (NGOs), private extension providers, or farmer associations, while fewer than 1% relied on alternative sources such as radio programs or farmer-to-farmer knowledge sharing (Figure 9).

These results indicate a strong reliance on government-led extension and reveal opportunities to strengthen complementary channels to improve outreach and encourage broader adoption of improved agricultural technologies.

Figure 9. Sources of agricultural extension services among respondents (n = 477).

3.12. Type of Extension Services Accessed

The majority of extension services accessed by respondents focused on crop pest and disease management, accounting for 284 responses (31%). In contrast, other services, such as crop valuation and irrigation awareness and maintenance, were accessed by less than 1% of respondents (Figure 10).

These findings suggest that extension programs in the study area are heavily focused on pest and disease management, while other critical areas, like farm economics and irrigation management, receive minimal attention.

To improve the overall effectiveness of the extension services such gaps should be addressed.

Figure 10. Type of extension services accessed by respondents. (n=917)

3.13. Level of Food Security in Season A 2025

During the last three months of Season A 2025, nearly 90% of all the respondents reported being food secure, while 14% experienced food security challenges over the same period (Figure 11).

These findings indicate that the majority of households maintained adequate access to food during the season; however, a notable minority faced food insecurity, highlighting the need for targeted interventions to support vulnerable households and improve overall food security situation in the study area.

Figure 11. Level of food security in Season A 2025. (n=399)

3.14. Major Pest and Disease Incidence (Season A 2025)

Figure 12 summarizes the reported occurrence of major pests and diseases that affected the different crops during Season A 2025. Respondents were allowed to mention all pests and diseases observed on their crops; as such, multiple responses were recorded per crop.

Results show that for mangoes, reported pest and disease incidences were equally distributed between fruit flies and mealybugs, suggesting that both pests posed comparable challenges to mango production during the season.

For non-industrial sugarcane, only one farmer reported growing the crop. This respondent identified termites as the primary pest affecting the crop, indicating a localized but potentially significant pest pressure.

Notably, the results show that among all responses related to coffee pests and diseases during Season A 2025, 37% of the responses indicate a high incidence of Coffee Wilt Disease, highlighting it as the most significant disease constraint affecting coffee production during the season.

Coffee is a priority crop in the district, being as one of the three key cash crops promoted under the Parish Development Model. However, the findings reveal a resurgence of Coffee Wilt Disease, which poses a serious threat to coffee productivity. Coffee Wilt Disease is a highly devastating fungal disease that causes massive loss of coffee trees, significantly reducing both yield and farmers' income.

The resurgence of this disease shows the need for targeted interventions, including the use of disease-free planting material, regular monitoring, and integrated disease management strategies, to safeguard the district's coffee production and maintain its contribution to household livelihoods.

Overall, the findings demonstrate that pest and disease incidence continue to affect a wide range of crops, with varying levels of prevalence, reinforcing the need for continued surveillance, early detection, and targeted pest and disease management interventions.

Figure 12. Number of responses by crop in relation to the different pests and diseases reported.

(n = 124 for banana; n = 250 for beans; n = 152 for cassava; n = 317 for coffee; n = 37 for groundnuts; n = 481 for maize; n = 2 for mangoes; n = 2 for oranges; n = 36 for pineapple; n = 10 for rice; n = 53 for tomatoes; n = 22 for sweet potatoes; n = 2 for papaya; n = 6 for soybean; n = 2 for watermelon; n = 12 for green pepper; n = 2 for jackfruit; n = 3 for industrial sugarcane; n = 1 for non-industrial sugarcane; n = 2 for vanilla; and n = 12 for cabbage).

3.15. Estimated Economic Loss Due to Pests and Diseases of Different Crops season A 2025

Pests and diseases affect farmers' income through two main path ways:

- I. Direct impact: Reduction in marketable yield due to crop damage.
- II. Indirect impact: Increased production costs associated with pest and disease management interventions.

Results show that the total monetary value of crop enterprises cultivated by respondents in Season A 2025 was UGX 1,339,701,075/= (One billion three hundred thirty-nine million seven hundred one thousand seventy-five shillings only). However, respondents were unable to realize UGX 282,581,101/= (Two hundred eighty-two million five hundred eighty-one thousand one hundred one shillings only) during the same season.

This unrecovered value is attributed to pest and disease attacks across different crops and represents the yield and income losses that farmers experienced in Season A 2025. Overall, this corresponds to an economic loss of 20.96%, as summarized in Table 4.

The findings show the significant economic burden that pests and diseases impose on crop production, highlighting the need for improved pest and disease management strategies and interventions to mitigate both yield and income losses for farmers.

S/n	Crop Name	Pest & Disease name	Total Production (KG)	Average price per Kilogram (shillings)	Total revenue (shillings)	Crop yield loss due to 2 major pests & diseases/kg	Percentage Loss	Economic loss (shillings)
1	Banana	Banana Bacterial Wilt Banana Weevil	84700	563	47,725,388	30629.6	36%	17,258,657
2	Beans	Bean fly Bean blight	49898	2,498	124,656,966	9395.77	19%	23,472,848
3	Cassava	Termites Cassava Mosaic Virus	87086.2	718	62,546,553	17015.6	20%	12,220,819
4	Coffee	Coffee wilt Coffee Red Blister	137729	4,603	633,931,202	30569.3	22%	140,702,486
5	Groundnuts	Groundnut Rosette Leaf miners	7845	2,957	23,200,695	2544.32	32%	7,524,550
6	Maize	Maize stalk borer Maize Smut	211141	904	190,923,607	47521.1	23%	42,970,833
7	Mangoes	Fruit flies Mealybugs on mangoes	190	1,263	240,000	190	100%	240,000
8	Pineapples	Pineapple mealybug wilt white leaf	66220	1,583	104,812,858	8068.04	12%	12,770,076
9	Rice	mottle Blast	2736.2	1,941	5,312,119	1157.62	42%	2,247,435
10	Tomatoes	Tomatoe Bacterial wilt Tomato Late Blight	30315	2,908	88,147,412	1157.62	42%	3,366,039
11	Sweetpotatoe	Sweetpotatoe virus Sweet potato Weevil	18560	815	15,126,400	8398.19	45%	6,844,525
12	Oranges	Citrus greening Orange dog	475	1,053	499,999	475	100%	499,999
13	Papaya	Fruit Fly Mealybug	1800	583	1,050,003	415.385	23%	242,308
14	Soybean	Soybean bacterial blight Soybean Leaf rust	450	4,360	1,961,931	281.25	63%	1,226,207
15	watermelon	Aphids	1600	750	1,200,000	800	50%	600,000

16	Green Paper	Fruit flies						
		Aphids	8500	925	7,862,500	2833.33	33%	2,620,833
		Anthracnose						
17	Jackfruit	Bacterial dieback	583	91	53,001	291.5	50%	26,500
		Leafspot						
18	Sugarcane Industrial	Termites	100000	145	14,500,000	5357.14	75%	776,786
		Insect borer						
19	Sugarcane non-Industrial	Termites	80	313	25,000	20	25%	6,250
20	Vanilla	Blackspot	50	9,000	450,000	0	0%	-
		Fusarium root rot						
21	Cabbage	Cabbage Black rot	10944	1,414	15,475,441	4924.8	45%	6,963,949
		Diamondback moth						
Total			1,339,701,075				21%	282,581,101

Table 4. Average economic loss due to pests and diseases for season A 2025

3.16. Common types of management options used by farmers to control pests and diseases for season A 2025.

Respondents were asked to indicate the different management options they used to control pests and diseases during Season A of 2025. The findings show that the majority of farmers relied on chemical pesticides to manage pests and diseases that affected their crops. Nearly half of all responses indicated the use of insecticides.

Notably, a small proportion of respondents (1%) reported that they did not use any control measures despite experiencing pest and disease challenges. The use of biological control methods accounted for 3% of the responses, while no respondents reported using acaricides (Fig. 13).

Figure 13. Pest and disease management options used by farmers during Season A, 2025. (n=1456).

4.0. SURVEY CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

While the survey provides important insights into crop production, pest and disease prevalence, and associated economic losses during Season A 2025, some limitations and challenges affected data collection and coverage:

I. Sample size and response limitations.

The number of respondents was relatively small, which may increase the margin of error when extrapolating results to the wider population. Future surveys, such as the planned Season B 2025 survey, will cover a larger number of households, as the activity is now conducted routinely. Additionally, some crops or enterprise categories had very few respondents for instance, one category had only a single response limiting the robustness and representativeness of the analysis for those categories.

II. Limited participation from Lower Local Governments (LLGs).

Certain LLGs showed low engagement in the data collection exercise, which contributed to uneven geographic coverage and underrepresentation in some areas.

Despite these constraints, the survey successfully gathered valuable preliminary data, providing a baseline for future assessments. Addressing these challenges in subsequent rounds—through capacity strengthening, improved digital tools will improve data quality, coverage, and representativeness.

5.0. RECCOMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the Season A 2025 survey, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen agricultural production, improve data collection, and enhance farmer livelihoods:

Strengthen Data Collection, Analysis, and Use

- I. Prioritize data collection and management: Data collection, analysis, and dissemination should be treated as critical activities within the district agricultural system. Adequate resources, training, and oversight should be provided to ensure accuracy and completeness.
- II. Enhance digital data collection capacity: Officers' devices should be updated and upgraded as needed, and staff trained in digital data entry to reduce errors and system-related challenges.
- III. Promote data-driven planning: Decision-making at the district and local levels should be guided by evidence from reliable data, ensuring that interventions respond directly to observed constraints and opportunities in the agricultural sector.

Pest and Disease Management

- I. Strengthen surveillance systems: Regular monitoring of pests and diseases, particularly Coffee Wilt Disease, Fall Armyworm, and maize stalk borer, should be maintained to provide early warning and rapid response.
- II. Promote integrated pest management (IPM): Farmers should be supported with training, inputs, and technical advice on IPM strategies, including the use of resistant varieties, biological control, and safe pesticide application.
- III. Support post-harvest management: Increased access to tarpaulins and drying equipment, improved storage technologies like PIC bags should be encouraged to reduce losses caused by pests and diseases after harvest.

Enhance Agricultural Mechanization and Labour Management

- I. Increase access to mechanized services: The low levels of tractor hire (17%) and ox-plough use (13%) highlight the need to expand mechanization services, particularly during land preparation and planting periods.

Improve Community Engagement and Participation

- I. Strengthen household and community sensitization: Efforts should be made to increase community awareness about the purpose and benefits of surveys, encouraging full participation and accurate reporting.
- II. Enhance engagement of Lower Local Governments (LLGs): LLGs should be actively involved in planning, mobilization, and supervision to ensure equitable data coverage across the district.

Economic Planning and Risk Mitigation

- I. Address crop economic losses: The estimated economic loss of 20.96% due to pests and diseases shows the need for targeted support interventions, including subsidized inputs, access to disease-free planting materials, and crop insurance schemes.
- II. Promote high-value and resilient crops: Encourage farmers to adopt tolerant or improved varieties, particularly for priority crops such as coffee, maize, and cassava, to reduce losses and improve income stability.

Implementing these recommendations will enhance agricultural productivity, reduce economic losses, improve farmer income, and strengthen the district's data-driven decision-making framework. Prioritizing surveillance, mechanization, and community engagement is essential for sustainable agricultural development in Kayunga District.

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APPENDIX

Units of measure used		
Item	Units	Units of measure
Banana		Bunches
	38kg	Biggest bunch
	28kg	Medium bunch
	15kg	Small bunch
Cassava		
	10tones about 55bags of 180kg@	
	15tonnes, about 83bags of 180kg	Medium tipper, fresh weight, payload
	20 tons, about 111bags of 180kg per bag	Larger tipper, fresh weight, payload
	10tones about 200bags of 50kg@	Smaller tipper, Dry weight, Payload
	15tonnes, about 300bags of 50kg	Medium tipper, Dry weight, Payload
	20 tons, about 400bags of 50kg per bag	Larger tipper, Dry weight, Payload
	150kg-200kg	Sack, fresh weight
	40-60kg	Sack, Dry weight
	35kg-45kg	Dry matter content of fresh cassava roots
Tomatoes	90kg	Big box
	60kg	Crate (Kenya)
	30kg	Small box
	15kg	basin (kataasa)
Beans	15kg	Basin, fresh unpoded
	5kg	Basin,fresh podded
	100kg-120kg	Sack (dry beans)
	20kg	Dry beans basin
Coffee	60-80kg	Sack (dry kibooko)
Soy bean	100-120kg	Sack,dry
	10-20kg	Basin,dry
Sweetpotatoo	100-140kg	Sack, fresh weight
	10-20kg	Tins
Watermelon	1-3kg	Piece, fresh
Green pepper	80kg-120kg	Big sack
	40-50kg	Small sack, crate
Cabbage	2kg-2.5kg	Small size

	3kg-4kg	medium
	3kg-5kg	Large
	130-150 heads	Sack
	30-45heads	Box(10-15kg)
Pineapple	1-3kg	Piece, fresh
	40kg	sack
Maize	90kg-100kg	Sack, Dry
Rice	50kg-80kg	Sack, Un-milled
	80-100kg	milled
	60-65kg	100kg of paddy gives 60-65kg of milled
Groundnuts	100kg-120kg	Sack, Dry, shelled
	45kg-50kg	Sack, dry, unshelled
	5-10kg	Basin, dry, unshelled
	10-20kg	Basin dry, shelled
Mangoes	90-100kg	box, sack
Oranges	90-100kg	box, sack
Jackfruits	9-20kg	large
	3kg-10kg	medium
	11kg	Common average weight
Sugar cane industrial	1000kg	
Sugar cane for chewing	1kg	Medium- large 1stickmakes a kilogram and 2sticks of small make a kilogram
Papaya	1-3kg	Piece, fresh
	70-110kg	box fresh

s/n	Crop Enterprises	Number of responses for the use of the different pest & disease management options.										Total
		Acaricides	Biological	Cultural	Fungicides	Herbicides	Host resistance	Insecticides	Monitor	Nematicides	None	
1	Banana	0	1	39	10	4	1	39	35	1	1	131
2	Beans	0	11	6	21	42	2	137	30	1	1	251
3	Cassava	0	8	8	7	13	5	41	21	1	3	107
4	Coffee	0	4	64	33	19	6	132	8	3	2	271
5	Groundnuts	0	2	4	7	1	0	18	8	0	0	40
6	Maize	0	12	38	49	64	10	210	72	1	7	463
7	Mangoes	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	3
8	Oranges	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	2
9	Pineapples	0	2	1	3	3	1	16	10	0	0	36
10	Rice	0	0	0	4	0	1	3	4	0	0	12
11	Tomatoes	0	1	7	19	3	4	24	13	0	0	71
12	Sweet potatoes	0	2	0	2	4	0	10	8	0	0	26
13	Papaya	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	4
14	Soybean	0	0	0	2	2	0	3	0	1	0	8
15	Watermelon	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0	0	0	3
16	Green paper	0	0	2	2	0	0	4	3	2	0	13
17	Jack fruit	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1
18	Sugar cane	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
19	Vanilla	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	1
20	Cabbage	0	1	0	5	0	0	5	1	0	0	12
	Total	0	44	169	168	156	32	647	216	10	14	1456
	Percentage responses	0.00%	3.02%	11.61%	11.54%	10.71%	2.20%	44.44%	14.84%	0.69%	0.96%	100.00%

Pest and Disease Economic Loss for Season A 2024												
	Crop	Disease name	Number of responses	Percentage responses	Total of Households	Loss quantity /kg	Average cost (shillings) per bunch of unit kg	unit cost/kg	Total financial loss (shillings)	Total banana production (kg)	Total income (shillings)	Percentage loss due diseases
1	Banana	Black Sigatoka	93	34%	163	75803	12981	463.6	35,142,271			28%
		Bacterial Wilt	5	2%					-			
		Banana Weevil	76	28%		49582	12981	463.6	22,986,215			
		Fusarium	48	18%		125385			58,128,486	272146	126,166,886	46.10%
		Nematodes	48	18%								
		Drought	3	1%								
			273	100%								
	Beans	Aphids	76	29%	107	15495	3002	3002	43,262,040	61510	184,653,020	23%
2		Bean fly	71	27%							-	
		Anthracnose	36	14%							-	
		Bean blight	77	30%		12199.5	3002	3002	36,622,899	61510	184,653,020	20%
			260									
3	Cassava	Cassava brown streak virus	52	23%	107	26339	5050	5050	133,011,950	1216035	6,140,976,750	2%
		Cassava mosaic virus	54	24%		47978	5050	5050	242,288,900	1,216,035	6,140,976,750	4%
		White flies	72	32%								6%
		Termites	44	20%								
		Others	1	0%								
			223									
4	Coffee	Black Coffee Twig borer	102	41%		28372.5	4000	4000	113,490,000	94173	376,692,000	30%
		Coffee red blister	85	35%	119	26456.5	4000	4000	105,826,000	94173	376,692,000	28%
		Coffee wilt	33	13%								58%

		Scales	26	11%								
			246									
5	Groundnuts	Aphids	26	34%	37	2782	921	1001.785714	2,786,968	28270	28,320,482	10%
		Groundnut rosette	19	25%		1210.5	1001.79	1001.785714	1212661.607	28270	28320482.14	4%
		Leaf miners	16	21%								14%
		Leaf spot	15	20%								
			76									
6	Maize	fall army worm	248	45%	311	49447.9	500	500	24,723,940	401081	200,540,500	12%
		Gray leaf spot	14	3%							-	
		Maize ear rot	44	8%							-	
		Maize head smut	90	16%							-	
		Maize stalk borer	155	28%		32409.5	500	500	16,204,750	401081	200,540,500	8%
			551									
7	Mangoes	Fruitflies	3	27%	4	510.625	736.84	736.84	376248.925	2660	1959994.4	19%
		Insects mealybugs	2	18%		154.375	736.84	736.84	113749.675	2660	1959994.4	6%
8	Oranges	Citrus greening	2	33%	4	356.25	105.26	105.26	37498.875	950	99997	38%
		Orange Scabs	4	67%		475	105.26	105.26	49998.5	950	99997	50%
			6									
9	Pineapples	Pineapple Mealybug wilt	5	33%		7833.5	1000	1000	7,833,500	33080	33,080,000	24%
		Phytophthora Heart rot	3	20%					0			
		White leaf spot	2	13%					0			
		Mealybug & Scales	5	33%		686.5	1000	1000	686,500	33080	33,080,000	2%
			15									
10	Rice	Blast Panicle	4	27%	11	1636.25	2171.42	2171.421	3552987.611	11305	24,547,914	14%
		Stalk borer	4	27%		1402.5	2171.42	2171.421	3045417.953	11305	24,547,914	12%
		Rice yellow mottle virus	2	13%								
		Rice Leaf Blast	4	27%								
		Sheath blast	1	7%								
			15									
11	Tomatoes	Leaf miners (tuta absoluta)	14	36%	19	3127.5		1666.67	5,212,510	35370	58,950,118	9%
		Bacterial Wilt	7	18%				1666.67	-	35370	58,950,118	0%
		Tomato late blight	16	41%		8603.75		1666.67	14,339,612			
		Septoria leaf spot	2	5%								
			39									
12	Sweetpotatoe	Sweetpotatoe butterfly/Caterpillar	55	55%	64	9751.88		250	2437968.75	158132	39,533,000	6%
		Sweetpotatoe virus	3	3%					0		-	
		Sweetpotatoe weevil	41	41%		35476.9		250	8869218.75	158132	39,533,000	22%
		Others	1	1%								
			100									
13	Papaya	Aphids	1	50%	2	10		500	5000	940	470000	1%
		Papaya Ring spot	1	50%		225		500	112500	940	470000	24%
			2									
14	Soybean	Army worm	23	49%	24	302		2000	604000	1414	2828000	21%
		Soybean bacterial blight	3	6%							0	
		Soybean Leaf rust	21	45%		276.75		2000	553500	1414	2828000	20%
			47									
15	watermelon	Aphids	2	22%	5							
		Fruit flies	3	33%		656.75		2000	1313500	18066	36132000	4%
		Leaf spot	3	33%		3156.75			6313500		36132000	17%
		mildews	1	11%								
			9									

S/N	Crop	Pest & Disease name	Number responses	of	Percentage responses	Total Number of responses
1	Banana	Black Sigatoka	93		34%	273
		Banana Weevil	76		28%	
	Beans	Aphids	76		29%	260
2		Bean blight	77		30%	
3	Cassava	Cassava brown streak virus	52		23%	223
		Cassava mosaic virus	54		24%	
4	Coffee	Black Coffee Twig borer	102		41%	246
		Coffee red blister	85		35%	
5	Groundnuts	Aphids	26		34%	76
		Groundnut rosette	19		25%	
6	Maize	fall army worm	248		45%	551
		Maize stalk borer	155		28%	
7	Mangoes	Fruit flies	3		60%	5
		Insects mealybugs	2		40%	
8	Oranges	Citrus greening	2		33%	6
		Orange Scabs	4		67%	
9	Pineapples	Pineapple mealybug wilt	5		33%	15
		Mealybug & Scales	5		33%	
10	Rice	Panicle blast	4		27%	15
		Stalk borer	4		27%	
11	Tomatoes	Leaf miners (tuta absoluta)	14		36%	39
		Tomato late blight	16		41%	
12	Sweet potatoes	Sweet potato butterfly/Caterpillar	55		55%	100
		Sweetpotatoe weevil	41		41%	
13	Papaya	Aphids	1		50%	2
		Papaya Ring spot	1		50%	
14	Soybean	Army worm	23		49%	47
		Soybean Leaf rust	21		45%	
15	watermelon	Fruit flies	3		33%	9
		Leaf spot	3		33%	